

Seoul Virus: A Public Health Challenge

A. P. Suthar, R. Kumar*, D. N. Nayak and C. V. Savalia

Department of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, College of Veterinary science & Animal Husbandry, Kamdhenu University, Navsari-396 450, Gujarat. India

Introduction

Seoul virus is a rodent-borne public health challenging Hantavirus found worldwide and is one of multiple hantaviruses belonging to family *Bunyaviridae* and genus *Hantavirus* that cause hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome (HFRS), mainly in Europe and Asia. Seoul virus was first described by Dr. Ho-Wang Lee, a virologist, in Korea in 1982. It was originally assumed that hemorrhagic fever was caused due to contact with field mice (Genus *Apodemus*), but Dr. Lee found that it could also be caused by contact with brown or Norway rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). As the infection was first discovered in an apartment in Seoul, the capital of South Korea the virus was named "Seoul Virus" (Lee *et al.*, 1982). Seoul virus falls under BSL-3.

Etiology

Hantaviruses belong to family *Bunyaviridae* and genus *Hantavirus*. Important species of hanta virus are Hantaan virus, Seoul virus, Puumala virus, Sin Nombre virus and Dobrava-belgrade virus (Schmaljohn and Hjelle., 1997).

Viruses in the *Hantavirus* genus are enveloped and contain a genome composed of three single-stranded RNA segments designated large (L), medium (M), and small (S) based on size. The hantavirus L segment encodes the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase, M encodes two envelope glycoproteins (G1 and G2), and S encodes the nucleocapsid protein (N) (Schmaljohn , 1990).

Host Range

The natural host of Seoul virus is major provocative such as Norway rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) and the black rat (*Rattus rattus*). This virus has been found in both pet rats and wild rat populations around the world (Lee *et al.*, 1982).

Transmission

Rats when infected act as reservoirs for the rest of their lives and will shed the virus intermittently in their urine, feces, and saliva (Lee *et al.*, 1982). Transmission may also occur from rat bites or when contaminated secretions (urine, feces, and saliva) come in direct contact with abraded skin, mucous membranes, eyes, nose and mouth. Rats are immune to the virus, but humans can be infected through exposure to infectious body fluids (blood, saliva, and urine), aerosolized rat feces, or bites from infected rats (Goeijenbier *et al.*, 2015). When fresh rat urine, droppings, or nesting materials are stirred up during vacuuming or sweeping, the virions can get suspended into the air. In addition, individuals who work with live rats can be exposed to Seoul virus through bites from infected animal. Seoul virus is not known to be transmitted from one person to another. Once a person has been infected with Seoul virus, they are protected against it for life (Woods *et al.*, 2009).

Epidemiology

Human infections account for ~25% of cases of hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome in Asia (Yao *et al.*, 2012). The first detection of Seoul virus (SEOV) in humans in Europe, causing severe disease in a pregnant woman was in France in October 2012 (Mace *et al.*, 2013). As of 2015 the virus has been found in wild rats the Netherlands, and in both rodents and humans in England, Wales, France, Belgium, and Sweden (Goeijenbier *et al.*, 2015).

An outbreak of Seoul virus infected eleven people in the U.S. states of Illinois, Indiana and Wisconsin from December 2016 to February 2017. Individuals who operated a home-based rat-breeding facility in Wisconsin became ill and were hospitalized. It was found that the individuals had purchased rats from animal suppliers in Wisconsin and Illinois. Investigators traced the infection to two Illinois ratteries and identified six additional people who tested positive for Seoul virus. All these individuals recovered. Further investigation by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention revealed that ten additional states (Alabama, Arkansas, Colorado, Indiana, Louisiana, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, South Carolina, Tennessee and Utah) have been notified that that their residents may have infected rats. According to the CDC, this is the first known outbreak associated with pet rats in the United States.

Fig. 4: An outbreak of Seoul virus in different state of U.S. (CDC, 2017)

In the first report of evidence of Hantavirus in India, a multi-institutional study has confirmed 28 cases of infection among patients with chronic renal disease, ware house workers and members of the Irula tribe engaged in rodent trapping in the Vellore district of Tamil Nadu.

Fig. 5: Evidence of hantavirus in India (Mani et al., 2012)

There has been no documented case of Hantavirus disease from India prior to this, although serological evidence existed. The team investigated the presence of hantavirus-specific IgG antibodies in 661 people belonging to the different risk groups. In all, 38 seropositive samples were found using a combination of a commercial ELISA test followed by an indirect immunofluorescence assay. Western blot test confirmed the presence of anti-hantavirus IgG in 28 of these samples. Though they

have not been able to identify all the types of hantaviruses present in the population, they have evidence of the Seoul, Thailand and Hantaan types being present in the samples (Chandy *et al.*, 2005).

Symptoms

Symptoms of Seoul virus infection, which usually begin within 1 to 2 weeks after contact with infectious material, include fever, headache, back and abdominal pain, chills, nausea, blurred vision, flushing of the face, inflammation or redness of the eyes and rash. The incubation period varies from 1 to 8 weeks; however, most individuals develop symptoms within 1 to 2 weeks after exposure. Seoul virus infection symptoms can range from mild to severe. In the severe form of the disease, patients can exhibit bleeding and renal syndromes. Inapparent infections can also occur. Symptoms of the illness caused by Seoul virus usually begin within 1 to 2 weeks after exposure to infectious material. Rarely, it may take up to 8 weeks to develop symptoms. In rare cases, infection can also lead to a type of acute disease called Hemorrhagic Fever with Renal Syndrome (HFRS), which might include low blood pressure, acute shock, and acute kidney failure. However, Seoul virus infections are usually mild to moderate and the vast majority of patients survive. Complete recovery can take weeks or months. However, in the severe form of the disease, patients can exhibit bleeding and kidney involvement, and mortality occurs in approximately 1-2% of cases (CDC, 2017). Common clinical features include fever, myalgias, thrombocytopenia, leukocytosis, renal failure, and shock in the most severe cases (Escutenaire *et al.*, 2000). Elevation of liver enzymes is characteristic of HFRS caused by Seoul virus infection (Kim *et al.*, 1995).

Diagnosis

Seoul virus infection is diagnosed based on symptoms and laboratory testing. History of contact with rodents or of cleaning areas contaminated by infected rodents is important factors for causing infection. For confirmatory diagnosis blood tests are performed. Testing of rats is done using serology with an Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay-based test (ELISA or Multiplexed Fluorometric Immunoassay [MFIA]) and positives are confirmed by immunofluorescence. The serological assay "MIFA HANT"; will pick up cross reacting rat Seoul antibodies (CDC, 2016). The only serological assay available to define the serotype of a causative Hantavirus is the neutralization test. (Chu *et al.*, 1995). A Seoul virus infection was diagnosed on the basis of elevated immunoglobulin M (IgM) titers and a rise in IgG titer by using Seoul virus antigen. The identification of Seoul virus infection was confirmed by using a nested reverse transcriptase-PCR (RT-PCR) assay targeting the hantavirus polymerase gene (L segment) (Woods *et al.*, 2009).

Treatment

There are no specific anti-viral drugs for treatment of Hantavirus infections. Ribavirin used in clinical trials in China for HFRS has been reported to cause significant reduction in fatality. Ribavirin has been shown to reduce the illness severity and lower deaths related to hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome (HFRS) if used very early in the disease (Huggins *et al.*, 1991). Supportive care which includes fluid therapy aids in maintaining blood volume, blood pressure, and electrolyte (sodium, potassium, chloride) levels. Dialysis may be required in severe cases of kidney failure. If infected rodents have contact with local rat populations, the infection with Seoul virus could spread to non-infected rodents and consequently change the prevalence of this zoonotic disease, both in rodents and in humans. Because there is presently no effective treatment for Seoul virus infection, preventing infections in people is important. There is no treatment available for infected rats, and euthanasia is recommended (Escutenaire *et al.*, 2000).

Vaccination

The first hantavirus vaccine was developed in 1990 initially for use against Hantaan River virus which causes one of the most severe forms of HFRS (Lee *et al.*, 1990). It is estimated that about two million doses of rodent brain or cell-culture derived vaccine are given in China every year. The wide use of this vaccine may be partly responsible for a significant decrease in the number of HFRS cases in China to less than 20,000 by 2007. Other Hantaviruses for which the vaccine is used include Seoul (SEOV) virus. However, the vaccine is not found to be effective against European hantaviruses including Puumala (PUUV) and Dobrava-Belgrade (DOBV) viruses. The pharmaceutical trade name for the vaccine is Hantavax (Cho *et al.*, 1999). As of 2013 no hantavirus vaccine has been approved for use in Europe or USA (Schmaljohn, 2012). There is no WHO approved hantavirus vaccine available. However, at least three different inactivated vaccines, developed in Korea and China, are being used only locally. Many other vaccine approaches, have been investigated using both inactivated virus and recombinant DNA technology (Maes *et al.*, 2009).

Preventive and control measures

- ✓ Prevention of exposure and contact with rodent urine, feces, saliva, and nesting material.
- ✓ Proper cleaning and disinfection of areas contaminated by rodent urine, feces or saliva.
- ✓ Keeping home, workplace, cottage or campsite rodent-free by blocking openings that might let rodents in.
- ✓ Storing food, water and garbage in containers with tightly fitted lids
- ✓ Wearing rubber or plastic gloves and a high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filtered respirator while cleaning a confined space.

- ✓ Avoid sweeping or using a vacuum cleaner to clean rodent feces.
- ✓ Spray feces with a household disinfectant or a mixture of 1 part bleach to 9 parts waters with exposure time of 10 minutes.
- ✓ Wash gloves, mops in disinfectant and hot soapy water after cleaning of contaminated places

Conclusion and Public health challenge

Seoul virus infection is a rodent-borne public health risk and challenging viral infection caused by Seoul virus, genus Hantavirus of the Bunyaviridae family that is found wide spread as worldwide. Cases have been reported from Netherlands, Korea, England, France, Wales, Belgium, Sweden and U.S. It is transmitted to humans directly by contact with saliva, urine, faeces and blood of Seoul virus infected rats mainly Norway rat and the black rat, which is also present near human habitats. Symptoms include fever, headache, back and abdominal pain, chills, nausea, blurred vision, flushing of the face, inflammation and redness of the eyes and rash. In rare cases, infection can also lead HFRS, which might include low blood pressure, acute shock, and acute kidney failure. Confirmed of cases is done by using a nested reverse transcriptase-PCR (RT-PCR) assay targeting the Hantavirus polymerase gene (L-segment). There is no specific antiviral drug or vaccine available and treatment is limited to supportive therapy is leading challenge in present scenario. Prevention of exposure to rodent excreta is the best preventive strategy. For prevention of disease avoid contact with rodent excreta and proper cleaning and disinfection of areas contaminated by rodent urine, feces or saliva must be ensured to overcome the challenge.

References

- CDC (2016). Seoul Virus outbreak. Available on: <http://www.phac-aspc.gc.ca/lab-bio/res/psds-ftss/hantavirus-eng.php>
- CDC (2017). Multi-state Outbreak of Seoul Virus. Available on: <https://www.cdc.gov/hantavirus/outbreaks/seoul-virus/index.html>
- Chandy, S., Mitra, S., Sathish, N., and Vijayakumar, T. S. (2005). A pilot study for serological evidence of hantavirus infection in human population in south India. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 122(3): 211.
- Cho, H. W., and Howard, C. R. (1999). Antibody responses in humans to an inactivated hantavirus vaccine (Hantavax). *Vaccine*, 17(20): 2569-2575.
- Chu, Y. K., Jennings, G., Schmaljohn, A., Elgh, F., Hjelle, B., Lee, H. W., and Schmaljohn, C. (1995). Cross-neutralization of hantaviruses with immune sera from experimentally infected animals and from hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome and hantavirus pulmonary syndrome patients. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 172(6): 1581-1584.
- Escutenaire, S., Pastoret, P.P. (2000). Hantavirus infections. *Revue scientifique et technique* 19: 64–78.
- Goeijenbier, M., Verner-Carlsson, J., van Gorp, E. C., Rockx, B., Koopmans, M. P., Lundkvist, A., and Reusken, C. B. (2015). Seoul hantavirus in brown rats in the Netherlands: implications for physicians-Epidemiology, clinical aspects, treatment and diagnostics. *The Netherlands Journal of Medicine*, 73: 155-160.

- Huggins, J. W., Hsiang, C. M., Cosgriff, T. M., Guang, M. Y., Smith, J. I., Wu, Z. O., and Oland, D. D. (1991). Prospective, double-blind, concurrent, placebo-controlled clinical trial of intravenous ribavirin therapy of hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 164 (6): 1119-1127.
- Kim, Y. S., Ahn, C., Han, J. S., Kim, S., Lee, J. S., and Lee, P. W. (1995). Hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome caused by the Seoul virus. *Nephron*, 71(4): 419-427.
- Lee, H. W., Ahn, C. N., Song, J. W., Baek, L. J., Seo, T. J., and Park, S. C. (1990). Field trial of an inactivated vaccine against hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome in humans. *Hemorrhagic Fever with Renal Syndrome, Tick-and Mosquito-Borne Viruses*, pp. 35-47.
- Lee, H. W., Baek, L. J., and Johnson, K. M. (1982). Isolation of Hantaan virus, the etiologic agent of Korean hemorrhagic fever, from wild urban rats. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 146(5): 638-644.
- Macé, G., C. Feyeux, N. Mollard, C. Chantegret, S. Audia, J. M. Rebibou, G. (2013). Severe Seoul hantavirus infection in a pregnant woman, France., *Euro Surveill* 18, 17(2013): 20464.
- Maes, P., Clement, J., and Van Ranst, M. (2009). Recent approaches in hantavirus vaccine development. *Expert review of vaccines*, 8(1): 67-76.
- Mani, R. S., Ravi, V., Desai, A., and Madhusudana, S. N. (2012). Emerging viral infections in India. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, India Section B: Biological Sciences*, 82(1): 5-21.
- Schmaljohn, C. S., Chu, Y. K., Schmaljohn, A. L., and Dalrymple, J. M. (1990). Antigenic subunits of Hantaan virus expressed by baculovirus and vaccinia virus recombinants. *Journal of virology*, 64(7): 3162-3170.
- Schmaljohn, C., and Hjelle, B. (1997). Hantaviruses: a global disease problem. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 3(2): 95.
- Woods, C., Palekar, R., Kim, P., Blythe, D., de Senarclens, O., Feldman, K., and Smith, M. (2009). Domestically acquired Seoul virus causing hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome Maryland, 2008. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 49(10): 109-112.
- Yao, L. S., Qin, C. F., Pu, Y., Zhang, X. L., Liu, Y. X., Liu, Y., and Xu, B. L. (2012). Complete genome sequence of Seoul virus isolated from *Rattus norvegicus* in the Democratic People's Republic of Korea. *Journal of Virology*, 86(24): 13853-13853.

